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Local Government Legislative Councils And Accountability In Governance: A Study Of Delta State, 2014-2024

¹Ohwoyibo, B. O.; ²Davies, E. O.; ³Akujuru, C. A. & ⁴Egobueze, A.

^{1,2,3,4}Department of Political Science,
Faculty of Social Sciences,
Rivers State University, Nkpolu - Oroworukwo, Port Harcourt, Nigeria

²davies.emmanuel@ust.edu.ng

³chukwuonye.akujuru1@ust.edu.ng

⁴anthony.egobueze@ust.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

This study examined local government legislative councils and accountability in governance in Delta State. It explored the relationship between legislative councils and accountability and analysed existing accountability mechanisms. Structural functionalism was adopted as the theoretical framework, while a mixed research method was used, combining primary data (questionnaire and interview) with secondary sources. Data were analysed using mean and standard deviation, Findings revealed that the Nigerian Constitution empowers local legislative councils to make bye-laws for good governance and accountability. Mechanisms such as legislative oversight, standing committees, appropriation, confirmation of appointments, public hearings, veto powers, and impeachment serve as checks and balances. However, financial inducement from the executive arm has weakened the councils' ability to enforce scrutiny, thereby undermining good governance. The study recommended constitutional review to set performance standards, sanction poor performance, and strengthen oversight, particularly in financial management. It also urged councils to ensure committee resolutions are debated publicly before implementation to enhance transparency and accountability.

Keywords: Accountability, governance, constitution, legislative councils, local government, oversight.

INTRODUCTION

In every organization, be it public or private, large or small—accountability is fundamental to effective management of human and financial resources. It requires constant communication and coordinated action among those who control and distribute development funds. The legislature plays a central role in ensuring openness in government, particularly in the activities of Ministries, Departments and Agencies (MDAs) and the management of public resources. Ebonugwu (2020) stresses that legislatures are indispensable to democracy, having existed long before the rise of modern democratic systems. Emerging from medieval European civilization, legislative control over public funds dates back to the twelfth century. Boynton (2021) observes that the number of legislatures expanded after World War II as constitutions replaced older governmental systems, a trend that has persisted in the 21st century. Similarly, Yaqub (2014) links the global spread of democracy to the popularity of legislatures, which provide broader representation by enabling informed and active participation of citizens.

In Nigeria, the legislature constitutes the heart of representative democracy, providing transparency and accountability in governance. Representation, lawmaking, and oversight remain its core responsibilities (Baskin, 2013). Orluwene (2014) regards the legislature as the highest branch of state power, serving as the voice of the people. In liberal democracies, the people exercise power indirectly through their representatives, who also occupy roles in the executive and judiciary. The legislature is therefore not merely symbolic but a battleground for competing political forces and interests. Njemanze (2013) emphasizes that in democratic societies, legislatures must hold the executive and other branches accountable. Egobueze (2020) calls it a monument to democracy, through which citizens express their will. Beyond appropriating money to the state, legislatures also monitor its expenditure, thus acting as guardians of public funds (Egobueze, 2016). Benjamin (2010) underscores that legislatures are foundational institutions that sustain democracy.

Abraham Lincoln's classic definition of democracy as government of the people, by the people, and for the people remains relevant. Okoosi-Simbine (2010) notes that this perspective highlights the legislature's importance as the nerve centre of representative government. In contrast, authoritarian regimes may operate by decrees without legislative input. Thus, legislatures provide indirect citizen participation and legitimacy in liberal democracies. Fashagba (2013) adds that the existence of legislatures ensures that electorates exert some control over public decisions that affect daily life.

Accountability, a core element of both corporate and democratic governance, demands that officials be answerable for their actions, policies, and spending. It exemplifies the need for stewardship reports to citizens. Pelizzo (2013) regards accountability as a procedural requirement of effective legislatures. According to Egobueze and Anthony (2020), accountability entails being answerable to those who have entrusted power and resources. Legislators, through questions and oversight, demand answers from agencies and civil servants. Accountability requires adherence to laws, reporting on performance, and demonstrating that public tasks have been executed according to agreed standards. The World Bank (2012) defines accountability as a governance strategy rooted in legitimacy and effectiveness. Kraai *et al* (2017) explain that oversight committees are critical in this regard.

Nevertheless, as Nigeria continues to struggle with accountability question, half of its population live in poverty due to corruption, theft, and mismanagement of funds. Many local governments fail to account for the large allocations they receive, resulting in poor growth. Accountability requires transparency, adherence to the law, regulation, prudent judgment, and independent review of actions. Yet, corruption has undermined prospects for local government autonomy, as many officials prioritize personal enrichment. Persistent accountability failures show that multiparty democracy has not significantly improved governance outcomes. Constitutions generally empower legislatures to supervise government agencies and enforce accountability, but weak institutional performance often undermines this role.

Given these realities, legislative oversight is justified to ensure resources are used efficiently to promote growth and service delivery. Holding leaders accountable prevents abuse of authority and resources. As Baskin (2013) notes, accountability is central to democratic governance, compelling managers in the public sector to adopt professional and transparent practices. Fashagba (2013) reinforces that accountability defines how public officials must justify their decisions or non-decisions. At the local level, government serves as the framework for administrative, executive, and legislative roles. Its objectives include decentralization, integration, grassroots participation, and efficient governance. When accountable, it can guarantee effective administration, quality service delivery, and participatory development. Local governments are expected to mobilize resources and deploy fiscal allocations to provide infrastructure.

The lack of accountability in Nigeria's local government system highlights broader challenges in democratic governance. Without transparency and oversight, development funds are mismanaged, leading to underdevelopment and public distrust. The legislature's role in ensuring accountability therefore remains vital, not only as a symbol of representation but as a mechanism for good governance and economic growth. Based on the foregoing, the paper posed the question: What is the relationship between local government legislative councils and accountability in governance in Delta State?

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The theoretical framework that directed this study is structural functional theory, often called structural functionalism. According to Mazi (2006), the theory was first applied by anthropologists Radcliffe-Brown and Bronislaw Malinowski. Radcliffe-Brown's works *The Andaman Islanders* (1922) and *Structure and Function in Primitive Society* (1952) demonstrate this approach, while Malinowski also applied it in his 1952 studies of African and Australian societies. Mazi (1960), in *Introduction to the Politics of Developing Areas*, explained how Almond and Coleman extended structural functional theory to comparative politics. Other contributors include Herbert Spencer, Talcott Parsons, Emile Durkheim, and Robert K. Merton, who used the theory to explain social systems and their interdependencies.

From this perspective, society is a network of interdependent institutions designed to meet members' needs. Institutions such as government, education, healthcare, religion, and the economy all function like the organs of the human body (Spencer's analogy), working together for stability. Durkheim emphasized society as a complex web of interrelated parts that, when functioning properly, foster stability. Radcliffe-Brown stressed that repeated social actions contribute to continuity and equilibrium. Merton (1968) noted that social processes often serve multiple purposes.

Despite its strengths, structural functionalism has faced criticisms. One major weakness is its inability to adequately explain social change. Critics argue that it is circular: repetitive patterns are assumed to have functions simply because they are observed repeatedly. Furthermore, dysfunctions may persist without benefiting society, contradicting the theory's assumptions. As a result, many sociologists consider functionalism weak at the macro level, though it remains relevant for mid-level research.

Structural functionalism has implications for democratic governance. Omotola (2019) observes that democracies depend on legislatures, constitutionally established to stabilize political systems and enact laws. Igwe (2015) explains that the theory presupposes knowledge of how a political system functions, which requires attentiveness to institutional performance. Thus, the stability of Nigeria's democracy is tied to the effective operation of its institutions; namely, the legislature, executive, judiciary, political parties, and interest groups. These institutions shape citizens' behavior and living conditions. Strong institutions are necessary to safeguard society against human weaknesses. Effective governance, especially in service delivery and infrastructure, requires not only sound laws but also mechanisms to monitor agencies' compliance. Here, the legislature plays a pivotal role. Omotola (2019) further describes it as a constitutional instrument of consent, legitimizing policies that serve the wider community.

The 1999 Constitution of Nigeria (as amended) provides for a federal system with legislative, executive, and judicial branches, all empowered by the same constitution. Stability depends on each arm performing its function: the legislature makes laws, the executive implements them, and the judiciary resolves disputes. Critically, the legislature must exercise oversight of the executive to guarantee accountability. The constitution grants it power to supervise government agencies and ensure effective policy implementation. Frolick (2016) insists that lawmakers have both legitimacy and responsibility to hold governments accountable. Ojo and Omotola (2014) add that legislatures subject ministries and departments to public scrutiny, approve or reject presidential nominations, and monitor executive performance. This includes confirming or rejecting ministers, ambassadors, justices, and other high-level appointees. Oversight ensures that public funds are expended as intended.

This framework aligns with the study's objectives because it emphasizes the interdependence of social structures and their functions. For instance, Nigerian local governments consist of structures such as Executive Chairmen, Vice Chairmen, Secretaries, Councillors, Supervisory Councillors, and Heads of Departments (Okoli, 2005). While local councils perform legislative duties, these other actors carry out social functions necessary for development. From a functionalist perspective, local government resembles a living organism, when diseased by corruption or inefficiency, the entire system fails. This analogy helps explain why Nigeria's local governments often lag behind global trends in democratization and governance.

Through the application of structural functionalism, the study examined how institutions can be strengthened to achieve stability and effectiveness. Just as healthy organs sustain a body, effective

institutions ensure accountability, service delivery, and grassroots development. Conversely, dysfunction at the local level undermines democratic governance and widens the gap between Nigeria and international standards. The framework therefore provides a basis for proposing practical measures to align Nigerian local governments with global benchmarks of effective leadership.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a mixed-method research design, integrating primary and secondary data to explore the phenomenon. The design enabled comprehensive data collection and analysis, facilitating generalization of findings. Delta State is made up of twenty-five local government councils that are divided into three senatorial districts. The local government areas are shown in table 1 below:

Table 1: List of Local Government Areas and their Senatorial Districts in Delta State

S/N	Delta Central	Delta North	Delta South
1	Ethiope West	Aniocha North	Bomadi
2	Ethiope East	Aniocha South	Burutu
3	Okpe	Ika North East	Isoko North
4	Sapele	Ika South	Isoko South
5	Udu	Ndokwa East	Patani
6	Ughelli north	Ndokwa West	Warri North
7	Ughelli south	Oshimili North	Warri South
8	Uvwie	Oshimili South	Warri South West
9		Ukwuani	

Source: Field Work, 2024

Yet, fifteen(15) LGUs were chosen at random using population density and economic potential as criteria for this investigation. The sample population for this research consists of the 10,662 people employed by the fifteen local government councils' administrative and legislative divisions. The following is a breakdown of the population based on senatorial districts and local government councils.

Table 2: Population of selected Local Government according to Senatorial Districts

S/N	Delta Central	Staff Strength	Delta North	Staff Strength	Delta South	Staff Strength
1	Sapele	811	Ika North East	714	Bomadi	610
2	Udu	710	Ika South	712	Isoko South	711
3	Ughelli North	711	Ndokwa East	710	Patani	710
4	Ughelli South	811	Oshimili North	710	Warri South	812
5	Uvwie	710	Ukwuani	610	Warri South West	610
Total		3753		3456		3453

Source: Ministry of Local Government, 2023

The study population comprised legislative and administrative staff across fifteen local government councils. Using Taro Yamane’s formula at 0.05 significance level, a sample size of 386 was determined. Questionnaires were allocated purposively due to uneven staff distribution: 270 for legislative staff and 116 for administrative staff.

Primary data were obtained through questionnaires and interviews, ensuring reliability and validity. A total of 386 questionnaires were administered, structured with closed-ended questions based on a four-point Likert scale (Strongly Agree = 4 to Strongly Disagree = 1). The benchmark mean was 2.50; items above were accepted, while those below were rejected. Interviews were also conducted with 30 purposively selected participants across the councils to capture insights not observable through surveys. Secondary data were drawn from books, journals, reports, newspapers, government publications, and online sources. Instruments were reviewed by supervisors and experts for face and content validity.

Reliability was tested through triangulation, with consistent agreement from over 90% of evaluators confirming their dependability.

Data were organized, tabulated, and analyzed using mean and standard deviation to assess patterns and variations. Hypotheses were tested with Chi-square (X^2) at a 0.05 significance level. The decision rule was to reject the null hypothesis if the calculated Chi-square exceeded the table value. This methodological approach ensured accuracy, credibility, and robustness of the research findings.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Presentation of Data

Table 3: Socio-Demographic Analysis of Response Rate

Administration of Questionnaires	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Number of questionnaires administered	386	100
Number of questionnaires not returned	36	9
Number of questionnaires retrieved	350	91

Source: Field Work, 2024

The table above reveal that out of the 386 questionnaire that were administered to respondents, 36 respondents making 9% of the questionnaire were not returned, 350 respondents representing 91% were successfully completed, retrieved and valid for proper analysis. The response rate is 91% which is a mark of excellent for the study.

Table 4: Socio-Demographic Analysis of Returned/Valid Questionnaire

Administration of Questionnaires	Frequency of Questionnaire Distributed	Frequency of Returned Questionnaire	Percentage (%) of Returned Questionnaire
Legislative Officers	270	250	65
Administrative Staff	116	100	26
Total	386	350	91

Source: Field Work, 2024

The table above reveal that out of the 386 questionnaire, 250 questionnaire representing 65% were returned out of 270 that were administered to legislative officers while 100 questionnaire representing 26% were returned out of 116 that were administered to administrative respondents making a total of 91%. The response rate of total questionnaire returned is 91% which is a mark of excellent for the study.

Table 5: Socio-Demographic Analysis of Gender

Gender of Respondents	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Male	200	57
Female	150	43
Total	350	100

Source: Field Work, 2024

Table 5 above shows that 200 respondents representing 57% are male while 150 respondents representing 43% are female. This indicates that the respondents are mainly dominated by the male. Irrespective of their genders, their responses do not in any way interfere with the outcomes of the study.

Table 6: Socio-Demographic Analysis of Academic Background

Educational Qualifications	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
FSLC	50	14
SSCE	90	26
HND/BSc/PGD	110	31
MSc/MPA/MBA/PhD	100	29
Total	350	100

Source: Field Work, 2024

The table above depicts the educational qualifications of respondents and thus revealed that 50 respondents representing 14% possess FSLC; 90 representing 26% acquired SSCE; 110 respondents making 31% possess the Higher National Diploma (HND)/Bachelor of Science (BSc) and Postgraduate Diploma (PGD) while 100 respondents representing 29% are holders of Master of Business Administration (MBA)/Master of Public Administration (MPA)/Master of Science (M.Sc) and Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D). This shows that the staff are dominated by different levels of graduates with various degree of certificates. This suggests that the respondents have good knowledge about local government legislative councils and accountability in governance in Delta State.

Table 7: Socio-Demographic Analysis of Length of Service in the Council

Number of Years	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
01 – 09	40	11
10 – 20	100	29
21 – 30	200	57
31 – above	10	3
Total	350	100

Source: Field Work, 2024

The table above shows that 40 (11%) of the respondents have been engaged or stayed in the service for a period between 0 to 19 years while 100 (29%) of the respondents have spent between 10 – 20 years. 200 respondents representing 57% fall between 21 – 30 years. 10 respondents representing 3% have spent between 31 years and above. By this presentation, it implies that most of the staff have spent reasonable number of years in the service. Thus, their responses have very serious implication on this study.

Data Analysis

Research Question: *What is the relationship between local government legislative councils and accountability in governance in Delta State?*

Computation of response rate on the relationship between local government legislative councils and accountability in governance in Delta State.

Table 8: Item showing the mean and standard deviation on the rate of the relationship between local government legislative councils and accountability in governance in Delta State.

S/N	ITEMS	Legislative Officers			Decision	Administrative staff			Decision
		N	\bar{X}	STD		N	\bar{X}	STD	
1.	Rate on relationship between legislature and accountability Legislature have significant roles to play in exposing corruption, inefficiency and	925	3.70	0.46	Agree	330	3.30	0.84	Agree

	waste through its oversight activities.								
2.	Legislature reduces friction and engenders stability in accountability and governance.	800	3.20	0.82	Agree	325	3.25	0.89	Agree
3.	Developing partner strategy would enhance effective oversight of the legislature in the area of accountability.	835	3.34	0.84	Agree	310	3.10	0.89	Agree
4.	Constitutional amendment would enhance legislature performance at all level of governance.	920	3.68	0.65	Agree	320	3.20	0.87	Agree
5.	There is a positive correlation between legislative executive relations in reducing accountability in governance.	920	3.68	0.65	Agree	335	3.35	0.73	Agree

Source: Survey Data, 2024

Benchmark 2.50

NOTE:

N= Numbers of scores in the distribution

\bar{X} = Mean

STD = Standard Deviation

The question of whether legislature have significant roles to play in exposing corruption, inefficiency and waste through its oversight activities, table 8 above on item I, has a mean of 3.70 from legislative officers which is above the benchmark of 2.50. Therefore, we agree that legislature have significant roles to play in exposing corruption, inefficiency and waste through its oversight activities. Item 11, which states that legislature reduce friction and engender stability in accountability and governance, this item has the mean of 3.20 from legislative officers is also above the benchmark of 2.50. Therefore, we also agreed that legislature has significant roles to play in reducing friction and engender stability in accountability and governance. Item iii, which states that developing partner strategy would enhance effective oversight of the legislature in the areas of accountability, it has the mean of 3.34 from legislature officers which is above the benchmark of 2.50. Therefore, we agreed that developing partner strategy would enhance effective oversight of the legislature in the area of accountability. Item iv, which states that constitutional amendment would enhance legislative performance at all levels of governance, it has the mean of 3.68

from legislature officers which is also above the benchmark of 2.50. Therefore, we also agreed that constitutional amendment would enhance legislature performance at all levels of governance.

In addition, item v, which also states that there is a positive correlation between legislative/executive relations in reducing accountability in governance, has the mean of 3.68 from legislative officers which is above the benchmark of 2.50. Therefore, we agreed that there is a positive correlation between legislative/executive relations in reducing accountability in governance. From the above analysis of table 4.6 on legislative officers, all the five items agreed and their aggregate mean were above 2.50. Therefore, the analysis of research questions from the responses of legislative officers has shown that local government legislative councils is related to accountability in governance in Delta State.

More so, the Administration staff have the following responses on table 8 above as stated below: The question of whether legislature have significant roles to play in exposing corruption, inefficiency and waste through its oversight activities, this item i, has the mean of 3.30 which is above the benchmark of 2.50. Therefore, we agreed that legislature have significant roles to play in exposing corruption, inefficiency and waste through its oversight activities. Item ii, which states that legislature reduces friction and engender stability in accountability in governance, this item on administrative staff has the mean of 3.25 which is above the benchmark of 2.50. We also agreed that legislature has the significant roles to play in reducing friction and engender stability in accountability in governance.

Item iii, which states that developing partner strategy would enhance effective oversight of the legislature in areas of accountability, it has the mean of 3.10 which is above the benchmark of 2.50. Therefore, we agreed that developing partner strategy would enhance effective oversight of the legislature in the areas of accountability. Item iv, which states that constitutional amendment would enhance legislative performance at all levels of governance, it has the mean of 3.20 from administrative staff which is also above the benchmark of 2.50. Therefore, we also agreed that constitutional amendment would enhance legislative performance at all levels of governance. Item v, which also states that there is a positive correlation between legislative/executive relations in reducing accountability in governance, it has the mean of 3.35 from administrative staff which is above the benchmark of 2.50. Therefore, we agreed that there is a positive correlation between legislative/executive relations in reducing accountability in governance.

From the above analysis of table 8 on administrative staff, all the items agreed and their aggregate mean were above 2.50. Therefore, analysis of research question one from the responses of administrative staff has shown that local government legislature councils in related to accountability in governance in Delta State.

Conclusively, research question one (1) which state that 'what is the relationship between local government councils and accountability in governance in Delta State, all the items in both legislative officers and administrative staff were above the benchmark of 2.50. Therefore, we conclude that there is relationship between local government legislative councils and accountability in Delta State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Local government legislative councils and accountability in governance in Delta State

The findings reveal that both legislative officers and administrative staff view the legislature as vital in exposing corruption, inefficiency, and waste through oversight. Legislative officers recorded a higher mean score (3.70) compared to administrative staff (3.30), reflecting stronger agreement on the legislature's supervisory role. Similarly, administrative staff acknowledged that the legislature reduces friction and enhances accountability, assigning a mean score of 3.25, closely aligned with the legislative officers' views. On partnership approaches, mean scores of 3.34 (legislative) and 3.20 (administrative) indicate consensus that collaboration improves oversight efficiency. Further analysis showed agreement that constitutional amendments could strengthen legislative performance, with mean scores of 3.68 and 3.20 respectively. Both groups also affirmed a positive relationship between legislative-executive interactions and accountability, with legislative officers scoring 3.68 and administrative staff 3.35.

A respondent emphasized that the legislative assembly is critical to local governance, empowered by the Nigerian Constitution to ensure responsible leadership and prevent executive excesses (P. Pere, personal communication, October 2, 2024). Supporting this, Ardigo (2019) highlights local governments as essential platforms for delivering public services and regulating daily environments. Indeed, decentralization fosters responsiveness and efficiency, enabling closer citizen engagement and more effective policy formulation.

The legislature plays a critical role in forging bonds between citizens and government, ensuring accountability and guarding against corruption, negligence, and incompetence. As O. As Timi noted (personal communication, October 2, 2024), legislative frameworks protect administrative systems from malfeasance. Decentralization has been advanced as a strategy to improve accountability by bringing governance closer to the people (Transparency International, 2009). While in some contexts it has encouraged citizen participation in local democratic institutions, in others it has fostered corruption through clientelism, state capture, and rent-seeking. Nonetheless, decentralization often strengthens local politics, communication, and responsiveness, although service quality remains uneven across countries.

Accountability emerged as a recurring theme among respondents. According to S. Idise (personal communication, October 7, 2024), reforms in Delta State aimed to close gaps between citizens and their local governments, stressing the need for transparency in financial stewardship. Accountability occurs wherever one party monitors or demands explanation from another. Joshi (2013) identifies four core elements: setting standards, gathering behavioral data, determining suitability, and sanctioning poor results. Accountability processes can be “invited,” such as participatory budgeting and anti-corruption hotlines, or “autonomous,” arising from grassroots mobilization. Their effectiveness depends on context, making outcomes difficult to generalize (Muriu, 2013).

Nigeria’s local government system has evolved through multiple reforms. Okeke and Agu (2016) highlight phases including local administration, democratization, separation of emirate/traditional councils from elected councils, and indirect rule. Nine significant reforms since 1976 shaped modern local governance: the 1976 Guidelines for Local Government Reform, the 1979 Constitution, the 1984 Dasuki Report, the 1988 Civil Service Reforms, the 1989 Constitution, the 1992 Local Government Handbook, the 1999 Constitution, and subsequent assessments in 2003. These reforms institutionalized democratic local governance, embedding accountability within legal and administrative frameworks.

Respondents linked reforms to greater transparency. As E. Allero (personal communication, October 7, 2024) observed, legislative councils have enabled more open communication between citizens and government, reducing service gaps. Awotokun (2001) similarly emphasized that Nigeria possesses institutionalized mechanisms for political accountability at the local level, though practices are not easily standardized. These mechanisms, grounded in the 1999 Constitution, empower state Houses of Assembly to interpret and implement provisions. Section 7(1) of the Constitution underscores the autonomy of local governments while mandating their accountability to citizens.

Overall, both field responses and scholarly perspectives affirm that accountability is central to effective local governance. Legislative councils serve as vital platforms for transparency, democratic control, and citizen participation, while decentralization, though uneven in outcomes, remains essential for making governance more responsive and inclusive.

The 1999 Constitution establishes democratically elected local government councils, requiring states to organize, finance, and operate them through legislation subject to Section 8. Awotokun (2001) notes that while all councils are constitutionally grounded, variations exist across states because Houses of Assembly enact different laws. Some states adopt a presidential model that separates powers, while others blend legislative and executive roles, reflecting either federal alignment or Westminster-style resource management. Regardless of the system, accountability depends on institutional instruments embedded in the Constitution.

Electoral processes form the first framework of accountability, ensuring officials remain answerable through periodic elections. However, in Nigeria elections are often compromised by irregularities and local godfathers, undermining their democratic role. The second framework is the legislative body, with

councillors elected to represent wards and oversee peers, promoting peer accountability. A respondent emphasized that legislatures restrain executive excesses and safeguard honesty and transparency (P. Pere, personal communication, October 2, 2024). Similarly, Ardigo (2019) stresses that local governments regulate citizens' daily environments, and decentralization enhances responsiveness by reducing the distance between decision-makers and citizens.

Respondents highlighted the legislature's role in bridging citizens and government, warning that without it, corruption and incompetence thrive (O. Timi, personal communication, October 2, 2024). Transparency International (2009) supports this, noting that decentralization can strengthen accountability and citizen engagement but may also encourage corruption such as clientelism or rent-seeking. In some cases, it revitalizes local politics and improves communication, though outcomes vary.

Accountability was repeatedly underscored. According to S. Idise (personal communication, October 7, 2024), Delta State reforms aim to close gaps between citizens and officials, ensuring transparency in managing public funds. Accountability as relationships where one party supervises or requests explanations from another, helping maintain public trust, prevent corruption, and reinforce democratic control. Joshi (2013) identifies four key elements: setting standards, gathering behavioral data, assessing suitability, and sanctioning poor outcomes.

Accountability systems can be "invited," such as participatory budgeting and anti-corruption hotlines, or "autonomous," driven by grassroots mobilization. Both are necessary, though their effectiveness depends on context (Muriu, 2013). Respondents confirmed that local reforms and legislative councils improve openness and communication, thereby reinforcing democratic governance.

In the main, Nigeria's constitutional framework mandates local government accountability through elections, legislatures, and decentralization. Despite electoral flaws and uneven reforms, both scholarly evidence and field responses affirm that legislative councils and accountability mechanisms remain essential for transparency, trust, and responsive governance at the grassroots level.

In this regard, Okeke and Agu (2016) observe that the Nigerian local government system has evolved through several phases, notably the system of local administration, the democratization of the system, the separation of traditional/emirate councils from democratic local government, and the native authority/indirect rule arrangement. These phases often overlapped and operated simultaneously. The most recent phase, however, is particularly significant for its profound influence on the growth and consolidation of local democracy. Within this period, no fewer than nine major reforms have been introduced. They include:

- a. a series of principles of the reformation of local governments in 1976;
- b. The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, ratified in 1979;
- c. The Dasuki Report published in 1984 on the Local Government System in Nigeria;
- d. Enhancement of the Civil Service of Local Governments in 1988;
- e. constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria which was adopted in 1989;
- f. A Handbook on the Administration of Local Governments that was published in 1992;
- g. constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, adopted in 1989;
- h. Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 respectively;
- i. The Local Government Councils in Nigeria were assessed in 2003.

Institutional processes operate as both inputs and outputs in local government administration, shaping accountability and transformation. Respondents noted that governments at all levels have introduced reforms to strengthen accountability, which enhances governance and allows citizens to benefit from the work of their leaders. Legislative councils now maintain open communication with other arms of government to ensure uninterrupted service delivery (E. Allero, personal communication, October 7, 2024).

Awotokun (2001) cautions against assuming that local governments lack institutional accountability. Instead, existing practices are embedded in the 1999 Constitution and interpreted by state Houses of Assembly. Section 7(1) guarantees democratically elected councils, requiring states to organize, finance, and operate them through law. Variations exist across states: some follow presidential separation of

powers, while others merge executive and legislative functions. Advocates of the Westminster model stress directing scarce resources to grassroots development, while presidential proponents emphasize consistency with state and federal systems. Despite differences, all approaches rely on institutional instruments of accountability.

Three structures hold Nigerian local governments accountable. First, the electoral system ensures regular elections, theoretically linking re-election to performance. Yet, elections have been undermined by irregularities and local godfather interference. Second, councillors elected at ward level legislate on behalf of constituents, reinforcing peer accountability within councils. Third, constitutional provisions establish intergovernmental oversight. The 1999 Constitution envisages supervisory relationships between federal, state, and local governments, but these mechanisms often fail to translate citizen preferences into responsive policies.

Financial accountability is also embedded in Section 162. Local government funds in the Federation Account are allocated to states and deposited in State Joint Local Government Accounts. While this arrangement ensures coordination, it often limits local fiscal autonomy. Obasa (2016) argues that a strong, efficient legislature is central to ensuring openness and accountability. Respondents agreed, stressing that accountability fosters trust, prevents abuse of power, and ensures service delivery (S. Ugwuoke, personal communication, October 7, 2024).

The 1999 Constitution vests powers in the legislature, executive, and judiciary (sections 4, 5, and 6). Among these, legislative checks are vital to holding governments accountable. Obasa (2017) reaffirms that good governance cannot thrive without an effective legislature. Madue (2012) outlines four reasons for legislative oversight: ensuring transparency by providing citizens with access to government processes; holding the executive accountable for its policies; scrutinizing and authorizing government spending to reduce inefficiency; and maintaining legal order by protecting rights and investigating abuses of authority.

In sum, Nigeria's constitutional and institutional frameworks establish multiple mechanisms of accountability in local government. Electoral systems, legislative councils, intergovernmental oversight, and fiscal controls are designed to promote transparency and responsiveness. However, their effectiveness remains limited by electoral malpractice, executive dominance, and weak financial autonomy. Strengthening legislative oversight and ensuring genuine democratic practices are therefore essential to consolidating accountability and deepening grassroots democracy in Nigeria.

Institutional processes function as both inputs and outputs in local government administration, shaping accountability and transformation. Respondents emphasized that reforms at different levels of government aim to strengthen accountability, thereby improving governance and enabling citizens to enjoy the dividends of democracy. Legislative councils, for example, now maintain open channels of communication with other arms of government to safeguard service delivery (E. Allero, personal communication, October 7, 2024).

Awotokun (2001) cautions against the notion that institutional accountability is absent in Nigeria's local governments. Rather, accountability practices are grounded in the 1999 Constitution and interpreted by state Houses of Assembly. Section 7(1) guarantees democratically elected councils, mandating states to organize, finance, and operate them through law. State variations reflect differing institutional preferences: some adopt a presidential model with strict separation of powers, while others merge executive and legislative functions. Advocates of the Westminster system highlight the need to channel scarce resources into grassroots development, while proponents of presidentialism emphasize alignment with state and federal structures. Despite these differences, all models rely on constitutionally sanctioned instruments of accountability.

Three key structures ensure accountability. First, the electoral system provides for regular elections, theoretically linking leaders' re-election prospects to their performance. However, electoral processes are often undermined by irregularities and the influence of local godfathers. Second, councillors elected at ward level legislate on behalf of constituents, reinforcing peer accountability within local councils. Third, intergovernmental oversight derives from constitutional provisions, which envisage supervisory

relationships between federal, state, and local governments. Yet, these mechanisms frequently fail to translate citizen preferences into responsive local policies.

Fiscal accountability is another dimension. Section 162 requires that local government funds from the Federation Account be allocated to states and deposited in State Joint Local Government Accounts. While this arrangement facilitates coordination, it also constrains local fiscal autonomy. Obasa (2016) stresses that a robust and efficient legislature is central to transparency and accountability. Respondents concurred, noting that accountability fosters trust, curbs abuse of power, and strengthens service delivery (S. Ugwuoke, personal communication, October 7, 2024).

The 1999 Constitution further vests powers in the legislature, executive, and judiciary (sections 4, 5, and 6). Among these, legislative checks are especially vital for accountability. Obasa (2017) affirms that good governance cannot thrive without an effective legislature. Similarly, Madue (2012) identifies four core functions of legislative oversight: ensuring transparency by making government processes accessible to citizens; holding the executive accountable for its policies; scrutinizing public spending to enhance efficiency; and maintaining legal order by protecting rights and curbing abuses of authority.

In conclusion, Nigeria's constitutional and institutional frameworks provide multiple mechanisms of accountability in local government; some of these are elections, intergovernmental oversight, and fiscal controls. However, their effectiveness is constrained by electoral malpractice, executive dominance, and weak financial autonomy. Strengthening legislative oversight and entrenching genuine democratic practices remain essential for consolidating accountability and deepening grassroots democracy in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

The study establishes that accountability in governance is closely tied to the activities of local government legislative councils in Delta State. The legislative council is essential to effective local government, as the Nigerian Constitution empowers it to legislate for transparency and accountability. Without this, governance risks executive rascality, arbitrariness, and corruption. The legislature therefore serves both as a watchdog over the executive and as an intermediary between the state and its citizens, balancing administrative misconduct and promoting honesty and responsibility.

Legislative oversight is a primary mechanism for ensuring accountability. Through committees, councils scrutinize public transactions, monitor compliance with procedures, and check arbitrary rule. This process provides evaluation, monitoring, and control over government agencies, policy implementation, and service delivery. When fairly applied, legislative oversight strengthens optimism in governance, though it remains vulnerable to corruption and political interference. Public hearings and complaint commissions further enhance oversight by exposing misconduct and giving citizens avenues to challenge maladministration. However, the effectiveness of legislative councils is constrained by excessive executive influence. The executive branch controls council pay, allowances, and fund allocations, creating unhealthy dependence on governors and chairmen. This political bond undermines legislative independence and threatens democratic accountability. Similarly, council expenditures are largely determined by executive estimates, limiting legislative discretion.

The research also highlights the need for reforms that enable participatory planning and empower legislatures to play their legitimate roles. Examples include the Delta State Electricity Power Sector Bill (2024), urban planning reforms, the establishment of local WASH departments, and the Local Government Law Amendment (2013). Such reforms, if implemented inclusively, can build trust, strengthen executive-legislative relations, and bring government closer to the people.

To improve effectiveness, legislative councils must implement recommendations from previous oversight before taking on new tasks. They also require adequate funding to carry out investigations, enforce compliance, and monitor legislation regularly. Increased resources would allow legislators to address practical challenges and enhance service delivery.

Overall, the findings confirm a positive relationship between legislative councils and accountability in local governance. Yet, this link remains weak due to political interference, poor funding, and structural

imbalances favoring the executive. Strengthening legislative independence, ensuring adequate resourcing, and institutionalizing checks and balances are therefore essential to deepen accountability and democratic governance at the grassroots level.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the study makes the following recommendations:

First, the Nigerian Constitution should be amended to establish clear standards for performance and accountability of local government legislative councils. Outdated provisions that excessively empower the executive weaken the legislature's effectiveness and encourage arbitrariness. A visible, active legislature fosters trust and confidence among citizens, while its absence risks executive rascality.

Second, legislative oversight must be carried out regularly by councils to review budget management, monitor corruption, and check executive high-handedness. Standing committee decisions should be transparent and communicated to the people, thereby strengthening good governance and political leadership at the grassroots.

Third, legislative councils must debate, amend, and pass local policies, particularly annual budgets. They should rigorously scrutinize income and expenditure statements presented by chairmen to ensure financial accountability. Excessive political interference should not deter the legislature from performing its oversight duties.

Fourth, local government legislative councils should enjoy financial autonomy to reduce dependence on the executive. Reliance has bred corruption, weak administration, and poor working conditions. Legislators must enact local laws to create sustainable revenue channels such as community markets, rental housing, farms, or small-scale enterprises thereby funding legislative activities without external interference.

Fifth, councils should initiate holistic and participatory reforms to enhance accountability and strengthen governance processes. They must be directly answerable to their constituencies through regular reporting and consultation. Furthermore, an independent institution should be established to monitor council performance, rewarding effective councils and sanctioning underperformers.

Sixth, local councils should focus on grassroots development by prioritizing human and capital projects such as employment schemes, rural roads, electricity, and water supply. Generating revenue through locally driven projects like filling stations, market stalls, or hospitality ventures will further strengthen development.

Seventh, new laws must curb financial misappropriation between governors and chairmen, and eliminate political godfatherism that compels legislators to serve patrons rather than citizens. Respect for the doctrine of separation of powers should be entrenched in the constitution to protect legislative independence.

Finally, effective implementation of reforms must be guaranteed. Good policies without execution are meaningless; therefore, government at all levels should ensure that laws and reforms passed are fully operationalized to promote transparency, accountability, and sustainable development.

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